

APPLICATION OF DRONES FOR PROTECTION AGAINST ANIMALS

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Abstract

Drones are small capacity flying vehicles that are mainly used for search, surveillance, security, transport of small payloads, recording observations, recording movies and photos over a widespread area. They are getting popular these days in the field of agriculture wherein they are used for supporting and encouraging the activities like field analysis, planting, crop spraying, crop monitoring, irrigation, health assessment etc. Recently, drones are also used for counting animals, keeping an eye on animal activities and their habitat. Such use of drones is currently under research and the new proposals are being developed. One of the most recent problems reported by farmers in India especially by the Hill farmers of Uttarakhand state is that of infiltrating animals that damage farms and associated produce. Hence, in this paper we propose use of drones as a solution for protecting farms and its produce against infiltrating animals like monkeys. A prototype has been developed for the implementation of the concept. In this paper we also discuss various methodologies, issues and challenges related with the application of drone for protection against animals.

Keywords: Drone, UAV, Agri-IT, animal infiltration, IoT supported protection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Drones have been around us for years. However, these devices have become more popular in recent times. The word “drone” has several different meanings and it originates from old English word *drān*, *drāen*, which means ‘male bee’. When talking about a drone as an electrical device, we are thinking of a remote-controlled pilotless aircraft. So, this unmanned aerial vehicle “drone” uses the definition as: “An unmanned aircraft or ship that can navigate autonomously, without human control or beyond the line of sight”. Another frequently used definition is: “Drone is any unmanned aircraft or ship that is guided remotely”. There is no doubt that drones are among the most advanced devices in today’s aeronautics, electronics, computer and robotics world [1-3]. Usually, drones are either fixed wing drone or multi rotor drones and are equipped with various kinds of sensors like optical cameras, optical gas imaging, multispectral, thermal, hyper spectral and laser/LiDAR (light detection and ranging) scanners [4][5]. Comparative

studies for the best drones in 2019 with pros and cons of each is presented at [6] and [7]. Battery life time for these drones lies in the range 12 minutes to 30 minutes. For more life time high capability batteries are required. These drones are equipped with 5 MP to 20 MP cameras that are capable to shoot images and videos at high resolutions in the range 720p to 1080p, 4K. They can be integrated to work with mobile phones as well [6][7]. Even underwater drones are gaining attention of professionals [8][9].

Drones as a device offers various advantages: (1) Drones are cheaper as compared to helicopters, (2) They can be charged electrically and as such very little cost is involved in terms of fuel and, (3) They are more maneuverable as compared to helicopters due to their small size. Drones devices also have various disadvantages: (1) Limited capacity battery is usually deployed on them which means lesser flight time, (2) Use of heavy battery means more weight and hence more power will be required for attaining altitudes, (3) Drones activity is limited by weather conditions: in rain and under heavy winds the drones flight suffers and, (4) Normally, the drones have limited flight range and can function with remotes within visual range [10].

The drone systems are becoming popular tools of conducting research, explorations and data acquisition projects. Their applications are increasing in a variety of fields. Some of the main areas of applications are: search and rescue, security, inspections, surveillance, science & research, aerial photography & video making, surveying & GIS mapping and, deployment of unmanned cargo systems [11].

Drones have been used extensively in agriculture. Drone technology is used as a tool for improving agricultural productivity, for disaster risk management and for community monitoring of forests. It is also used at different stages of cropping cycle like soil and field analysis, planting, crop spraying, crop monitoring, irrigation, health assessment. Some of the challenges related to the implementation of UAVs in the agricultural context are: acceptability on the farmer front, initial cost of purchase, good connectivity, weather dependency, flight time & flight range and, legal aspects of use [12].

Recently, drones are also used for counting animals, keeping an eye on animal activities and their habitat. Such use of drones is under research and the new proposals are being developed. One of the most recent problems reported by farmers in India especially by the Hill farmers of Uttarakhand state is that of infiltrating animals that damage farms and associated produce. Hence, in this paper we propose use of drones as a solution for protecting farms and its produce against infiltrating animals like monkeys. A prototype has been developed for the implementation of the concept. The paper summaries the methods used earlier for keeping the animals away from the farms. The special case for monkeys has taken discussed who are somewhat smarter than other animals.

This paper is further divided into 6 sections. Section 2 tells about the use and usefulness of drones against animals. Section 3 provides protection against monkeys using drones as a case study. A drone based methodology to protect against monkeys is proposed in section 4. As the

use of drones for protection against animals is increasing, section 5 presents issues and challenges. Section 6 provides discussions while section 7 concludes the paper.

2. EXISTING DRONE USES AGAINST ANIMALS

Use of drones in wildlife protection is also not new. Several efforts by researchers in the direction of wild life protection have been done. Prominent among them are:

(1) Use of drones in Niger, Africa to help monitor not only the endangered addax antelopes, but also the dama gazelle, and cheetahs that roam in the park [13],

(2) Use of drones by National Parks Authority, Tanzania to monitor people entering the parks and by Tanzanian army for anti-poaching operations. Even it is suggested to use drones to find the locations of the poachers and then direct local governments to the location of the criminals [14].

(3) Jarrod Hodgson and Lian Pin Koh working in the University of Adelaide's Unmanned Research Aircraft Facility (URAF) developed the notion of using UAVs as a powerful and low-impact ecological survey tool. Use of drones for conducting surveys implies collection of more precise observational data. The takeaway point from their work is that the animal responses vary depending on a variety of factors, including the species, environmental and historical context, and the type of UAV and its method of operation. Their work termed as “set of best practices for researchers to follow when employing drones around wildlife” has been reported in *Current Biology Journal*. As per the report steps should be taken to ensure that UAV operations are not causing undue stress to animals while surveying in the field [16].

(4) Research is being carried out for cattle farming in large grazing areas by using drone technologies for healthiness of animals, their enough food requirements as well as locating predators around the grazing areas [12].

(5) The National Parks in India is looking forward to completely adopt the conservation drones to monitor animal population and forest mapping. The merits and demerits of use of drones for the wildlife conservation and its habitat monitoring are presented at [17]. This work considers animal's psychological reactions like measuring heart beats through sensors to flying drones over them or near them. It is mentioned in their work that in one drone operations in Utah's Zion National Park (2014), mother sheep and their calves got disassociated with each other; due to which the park authorities have banned use of drones [18]. There are instances stating that drones are useful for finding and locating the endangered species like the Sumatran Orangutans. These animals are on the verge of extinction and lives on trees for their survival. They can be traced and rescued by using drones technology.

(6) One of the major uses of drones in the field of science these days is to use them to count the population of animal species and also to ensure the protection of endangered species by enabling the analysis of animal behavior [18].

(7) Monitoring of animal species for successful nature conservation purposes via drones is done by Gemert et al. (2015). Their work targets identification of species like rhino, elephant etc. using fully autonomous drones that captures high-resolution images and videos. They utilized application of existing three light-weight human centric image processing based object detection methods (color-DPM, standard DPM and exemplar SVM) for indentifying objects (animals) in images and counting objects (animals) in videos. They have also made their code and dataset available in public domain [19].

3. CASE STUDY: USE OF DRONE FOR MONKEYS

Drones have been used in a study (year 2018) in Mexico for monitoring the population of various species of monkeys like howler monkeys, spider monkeys and orangutans. In this study, thermal infrared (TIR) camera was fit on the drones for determining the population of spider monkeys. The TIR images were then used for identifying and counting the spider monkeys. TIR images served the purpose in this case as the spider monkeys have higher temperature as compared to their surroundings and they spend time over the forest canopy. The results were gathered at the sleep time of the monkeys at the sleep sites and validated using the ground surveys of the same sites by the staff members. During the drone survey period the behavior of monkeys was also studied and it was found that (i) Monkey children's continue playing even under drone activity, (ii) few monkeys changes their positions which they restored after drone moved away, (iii) several monkey showed no response to drone movement and (iv) sometimes a monkey screen in response to the drone movement [20]. In another similar study by Kays et al. (2018) on arboreal mammals in Panama, it was found that such method was pretty successful in the evenings but was less successful in the sunshine hour which is attributed to the fact that temperature difference between animals and canopy is marginal during sunshine hours. It was also found in this study that using TIP imaging detects high-canopy species but humans detect more mammals overall. Thus, use of cameras for the purpose of detection of monkeys has limited use as of now and use of high end cameras for the detection purpose will only add cost to the system [21]. Some other studies have also been reported using drones on monkeys mainly targeting either habitat or conservation issues [22][23].

An interesting study was conducted in which the green monkeys of West Africa were exposed to drones. This study was conducted because the scientists were not able to understand the behavior of green monkeys of West Africa when they were exposed to predator birds like eagle. Upon exposure to eagle, green monkeys do not emit any sounds. Otherwise, under threats from leopards and snake they emit similar sounds as that emitted by their cousins – vervet monkeys of East Africa. The scientist recorded the sounds upon exposure to drones. It was noticed that under

drone exposure, the green monkeys also emitted the similar alarm sounds as their cousin vervet monkeys. This study compared the behavior of monkeys with each other and summed that such responses are evolutionary in nature. Such alarming calls to alert other monkeys were termed as 'Eagle Calls'. It is clear that upon noticing drones the monkeys treat drones as predators, get frightened and emit the 'Eagle Calls' to alert the other monkeys in the group. This make drones the perfect selection for distracting monkeys and saving the farms from the monkeys [24][25].

4. PROPOSED DRONE PROTECTION SYSTEM AGAINST MONKEYS

Based upon the ideas mentioned in the previous sections, we propose a drone based system for keeping the invasive animals like monkeys, stray dogs etc. away from the farms. The proposed drone based system may be used by farm owners in case an invasion by these animals has been identified in the farms. In the proposed drone based protection system against infiltrating animals especially monkeys, two methods listed in Table 1 are proposed for frightening the animals. Method 1 listed in Table 1 is use of high frequency ultra sonic waves for frightening the animals. This method is motivated by the work done at [26] wherein it is proposed that use of high frequency ultra sonic waves may prove useful for frightening the animals. Method 2 listed in Table 1 is use of recorded sounds of persons, sound of crackers, sounds of gunshots, sounds of langurs etc. for frightening the animals. It has been shown experimentally that monkeys behave abnormally and feel stressed when exposed to high frequency ultra sonic waves or sounds very near to them. Initial chances are that the monkeys can get frighten and try to escape or run. Especially they are very much afraid of the sounds of furious dogs, crackers, gunshots and langurs.

Table 1: Proposed methods utilized for protection against animal infiltration.

S.No.	Method	Priority
1	use of high frequency ultra sonic waves	First
2	recorded sounds of persons, sounds of furious dogs, sound of crackers, sounds of gunshots, sounds of langurs etc.	Second

For implementing the method 1 listed in Table1, a sample programmable circuit board (PCB) (termed as repeller) is fabricated for emitting the ultra sonic waves. Figure 1 shows the circuit diagram of the proposed repeller in Multisim software. The waveform generated is shown in the output of oscilloscope, which shows the tune of 25 kHz frequency. The idea is to generate a varying frequency for frightening monkeys or animals upon switching ON (or powering ON) the PCB within the range of 25 kHz to 50 kHz.

Figure 2 (A) shows the breadboard circuit testing of the proposed circuit. The output of the circuit has been recorded on a Digital Storage Oscilloscope (DSO) and the speaker is used to test for the audio. Figures 2 (B) and (C) shows the signal recorded on a DSO with maximum and minimum frequency counter view. The Frequency recorded on the DSO show the range between 31 kHz to 64 kHz including the entire range for proposed application. Figure 2 (D) shows the prototype of the circuit that has been fabricated. This fabricated system is fitted over customized drone for frightening and scarring the monkeys.

For implementing the method 2 listed in Table1, a box containing Raspberry Pi (a small computer) and speakers with high sound capacity (having inbuilt battery) are fitted on the drone and programmed in Python language. In case speakers with inbuilt battery are not available, battery in addition to the drone battery may be used. For the experimental purpose, the Raspberry PI configuration used is: Raspberry PI3, Model B+ with WiFi and BLE, Raspberry PI camera, OS: Raspbian PI, other accessories that are used during working with raspberry PI are: 7 inch capacitive touch screen, 64 GB Class 10 SD card, Plastic Enclosure Case for RPi, HDMI cable, 5 V USB Power adapter, USB to Micro USB cable and network patch cable. The following are the specifications of the drone used: X-Shaped Quad copter, Radio Transmission Control, GPS Navigation System, Battery: 10,000 mAh, Flight Time: 20-25 Minutes, Range: 100 meter, Weight Lifting Capacity: 200-300 gm, 4 BLDC Motors, 4 Propellers.

As weight of the devices (PCB/Speakers/Battery/Raspberry PI/camera) is not on the higher side, we have used a small sized customized drone that has payload capacity of ½ KG. Thus, the customized drone is fitted with a box containing mini-computer (Raspberry PI), open source pilot module, Raspberry PI camera, speakers with high sound capacity and additional battery. The system named as Drone Protection System for Hill Farms (DPS-HF) is shown in Figure 3 (a). It is named so because of the systems usefulness and the utility to the Hill farmers of Uttarakhand state. The drone pilot can change/select from various options: high frequency ultra sonic waves, sound of persons, sounds of furious dogs, sound of crackers, sounds of gunshots, sounds of langurs etc. Mission Planner [27] which is a popular ground control station (GCS) software is used. It is particularly used by the drones running the ArduPilot firmware. It is a comprehensive tool designed for planning, simulating, and controlling unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) and other robotic systems.

The sounds of persons, furious dogs, crackers, gunshots, other animals like langurs etc have been stored and are selected by the drone pilot for frightening the animals. Presently two wireless techniques namely, Bluetooth and Wireless LAN (802.11) are being used for establishing the communication for producing the sounds by the pilot. The fabricated PCB that is capable of generating high frequency ultra sonic waves is also fixed on the drone. The drone pilot can change/select from options: high frequency ultra sonic waves and various sounds (persons/crackers/gunshots/other animals like langurs etc.). As these sounds are produced near to the monkeys, these prove to be effective in frightening the monkeys while causing no physical harm to the monkeys. Moreover, as the DPS-HF system operates at a distance from the monkeys,

the chances of attack or damage by monkeys on the operator (or farmer), is minimum. The developed prototype was shown at the various Kisan Melas – organized at GBPUAT, Pantnagar (Figure 3 (b)) where it was well appreciated by the farmers of the state.

(a) Developed prototype (DPS-HF) System under flight

(b) Showcasing the system at the Kisan Mela at GBPUAT, Pantnagar

Figure 3. Drone Protection System for Hill Farms (DPS-HF)

5. USE OF DRONES FOR PROTECTION AGAINST ANIMALS: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

A Blog on How drones protect animals [17] tells us that animals do get distressed hearing unusual noise from an unknown object. Another interesting fact regarding wildlife drones is identified in [26] which can be stated as – “Use of drones can scare invasive birds away from crops” [26]. Similar fact is also stated in [28] as – “Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), or drones, can help protect wildlife – but they can make animals dangerously stressed out”. These facts make us think that the animals can be kept away from the farms by utilizing drones and they may also be avoided from causing the damage to crops. The amount of stress caused in the animals needs to be studied as it may affect their habits, changes in hormones, reproductive cycles etc. The main point of concern in use of drones for animal protection is that such drones should never be used to torture the animals.

It is also perceived that use of high frequency ultra sonic waves often causes danger to the birds. It should also be kept in mind that use of drone technology which is successful against one kind of animals may prove to be unsuccessful against other kind of animals. Both these limitations can be overcome to some extent by using drone system for small duration, switching of ultrasonic wave frequencies and using drone systems only in the close vicinity of the animals.

However, use of drones is preferred as compared to the tethered aerostat systems. These aerostat systems [29] are nothing but static balloon systems tied to ground using tethered cable and filled with lighter than air (LTA) gases. It is because of the fact that drones provide localized protection against monkeys specific to only the areas affected (shown in Figure 4 (b) with smaller red circle) by the monkey invasions whereas the tethered aerostat systems provides animal protection system within its coverage area (shown in Figure 4 (a) with larger red circle) and hence may affect all the animals in that area irrespective of the fact whether they are causing some problems in farms or are enjoying their natural habitat. In case of deployment of intelligent systems over tethered aerostat systems as payload - continuous vigilance, monitoring and interpretation of animal activities is required which may increase cost of such systems. These differences are made clearer in the Figure 4.

Figure 4. Comparative visualization of the tethered aerostat systems and drone system for animal protection

Expertise is not only required to run the drone but also in use of these methods against animals. Flying at uneven terrain like in Hills is bit risky and the person may fall any time and hurt himself while concentrating on the drone and animal. Frightening the animals through drones with speakers by maintaining large distance may not be fruitful as the degree of fear in the animal becomes less with increase of distance. Weight and size of the box in which Raspberry PI is kept on drone needs to be small. Drone space adjustments and balancing needs to be done so that during application of drone system on monkeys problems may not arise and system behaves perfectly.

There are several potential obstacles in implementation of such systems. The cost of such systems will increase upon increasing the weight of the hardware like speakers and long lasting batteries. There are infact several regulatory concerns like dealing with animals (monkeys) have to be done in accordance with the prevailing laws of the state. This will require obtaining permissions from the regulatory bodies like forest department, ethics committees etc.

Venture firms and startups are also thinking on the same lines and are developing drones for protection against animals. Tokyo-based venture firm Skyrobot is planning to launch such drone with capabilities like auto detection of animals through infrared heat detecting cameras. Such developed drones will take necessary actions like making sounds of firecrackers and emitting high frequency signals. They are even thinking to drop a ball that will contain liquid with repellent odor. In order to add features to their drone the cost is expected on the higher side [30]. This should be reduced bearing in mind that most of the animals are active during day time only and the drone operations still require human interventions. Our prototyped system requires farmer/human intervention and also this is probably the first instance of equipping & controlling the drone with small Raspberry PI computer. It seems that Skyrobot's system is still in development phase and no prototype has been displayed. Also, in country like India most of the farmers are small i.e., these farmers own small size of land for cultivation and it is not practical for such farmers to invest handsome amount of money as evaluated by Skyrobot just for the sake of getting rid of animals like monkeys. Hence, it is essential that any such implementation of drones should be made cost effective instead of addition of more features like auto detection and use of high end cameras.

DISCUSSIONS

Agriculture drones usually operates at around 100-200 meters height above the target area. The altitude is maintained because: (1) after falling down from less height, drones suffers less damage, (2) at this height drones are less affected by winds and, (3) attaining more height will degrade the quality of images of the target area. The domain of protecting fields and crops from damage by animals require further less altitude. This is because close proximity of drones towards animal will mean more impact while frightening and chasing the animal. Moreover, animals like monkeys do not fly rather climb on trees after being chased which implies that the flying altitude of a drone should be as high as that of the highest tree in that area. The important points to realize are: (1) Use of drone for the work of protecting farms from animals means less stress and less danger to the human beings. An incidence needs mention here in which a human being tried to run after the monkeys on his rooftop and he fell off the rooftop due to monkey's attack on him leading to the fracture of his legs. (2) The alternatives (method 1 or method 2 mentioned in Table 1) of frightening the monkeys can be switched from the person (pilot) controlling the drones. So if drone pilot finds that the monkeys are not responding to a particular methodology, next method can be selected. (3) Less altitude/height means less power requirements, (4) Drone is effective when group of monkeys needs to be chased. Even multiple drones can be used in collaborative manner to chase a group of monkeys and, (5) The developed drones should be equipped with large number of sensors that protects them from collisions with other nearby objects during the flight. The drone pilots should remain cautious during entire drone run chasing the monkeys so that the device does not collide with nearby trees.

Use of methods like dropping stones, pepper, chilli powder bullets, tear gas etc. may harm the animals. Hence should be used carefully so as to avoid their direct use on animals. Infact, High court of Uttarakhand (India) has banned use of material like chilli powder for distracting elephants. They have ordered that the elephants has the first right to roam and use the forest area termed as 'Elephant Corridor' in Uttarakhand (India) [31].

Holland's study (2015) on Minnesota's black bears reveals that the heart rates (measured by sensors implanted in the bodies of animals) of these animals increases when they saw drones in the sky. The study also points out that wild animals will soon get adjusted to the drones as they have adjusted to the helicopters [16]. A comparative analysis with existing solutions or technologies used is obviously useful but in the present case this is not possible due to non-existence of such solutions.

CONCLUSION AND FUTRUE DIRECTIONS

Drone technology is stabilizing and its applications are on the rise. The drone's use towards finding animals, counting populations of animals, protecting animals and monitoring wildlife is increasing day by day [32, 33]. In farming, drone's major contribution is in crop monitoring and its application as precision tool [34, 35]. In this paper, we have touched a new dimension i.e. use of drones as a possible solution against protection from animals in the farms. The paper discusses in particular the case of protecting farms from monkeys. A prototype drone proposal has been put forward that switches among two possibilities: emitting the high frequency ultra sonic waves and making various sounds near to the animals. Issues and challenges that arise via use of drones for the purpose of distracting animals from crops are also highlighted. The main motive of the proposal is to distract the monkeys without harming them other animals species present nearby. It does not consider animal identification as this will involve additional cost of cameras and mechanism. Obviously, rise in the cost of such system will make it less effective for low earning farmers. It is evident from this work that low flying & low cost drones (equipped with Raspberry PI having inbuilt raspberry PI drone cameras with low payload) will be very useful for distraction of animals that cause harm to farm crops. We are in the process of developing such drone systems with reduced cost for distracting the monkeys.

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